

PlatFAMs

Methodology report

Documentation of PlatFAMs' three generational study: design, data
collection, sample and ethical considerations

Contents

- General overview..... 2**
- Background of the project..... 2
- Overview of the research design..... 4
- Data mangement and ethical considerations 4
- Recruitment of sample 5
- T1 Interview guide: Individual interviews 5
- T2 Interview guide: Family interviews..... 7
- Country specific overview 8**
- Estonia 8
- Spain 12
- Poland..... 15
- Romania..... 20
- UK - England 22
- Norway 24

General overview

Background of the project

The primary objective of PlatFAMs was to reveal and critically understand the conditions of family relationships with pervasive, all-encompassing digital platforms, and generate recommendations for diverse stakeholders regarding families' engagement with platforms. This was achieved through a close examination of family practices and intergenerational relations in contemporary digital society, specifically focusing on the interactions among three generations (children/youth 7-17 years old, their parents, and grandparents, along with other relevant caregivers).

Secondary objectives were to unpack relational and temporal aspects of digital platforms' wide-ranging social transformation (of everyday family practices and intergenerational relations in contemporary European societies) as expressed in three sub-objectives:

- I) to trace the impact of digital platforms through the life course as expressed in family practices;
- II) to better understand the negotiations between family members and across generations about the use and implications of digital platforms;
- III) to understand the meaning-making of how different age groups within diverse families create and co-construct imaginaries of digital futures.

Three thematic strands of the project were studied across families and generations. First, digital navigation and domestication, understood as the ways people interact with different platforms in order to identify inter-generational differences and similarities within diverse family structures. Second, digital negotiation and co-construction, understood as relational aspects within diverse family structures regarding connections and networking using digital platforms. Third, digital futuremaking as the process of anticipating and creating imaginaries of digital futures, both personal and societal, that shape present practices in ways that are consequential for families (Erstad & Silseth, 2019; Livingstone & Blum-Ross, 2020).

The PlatFAMs consortium represented a distinct European agenda on technological developments and the role of diverse families in our European societies. The project brought together a strong and complementary repertoire of interdisciplinary expertise necessary for this project.

The consortium consisted of:

	<p>Project leader and PI Norway Professor Ola Erstad from the University of Oslo, Norway. The Norwegian team included project coordinator professor Kristinn Hegna, professor Elisabeth Staksrud, postdoc Maja Nordtug, researcher Victoria de Leon Born, researcher Seffetullah Kaldas, PhD student Jo Fosby Jaavall and researcher Ole Smørdal.</p>
<p>TARTU ÜLIKOOL</p>	<p>PI Estonia Professor Veronika Kalmus from the University of Tartu, Estonia. The Estonian team included professor Andra Siibak, research fellow Signe Opermann, post doc Maris Manniste, Dr. Marit Sukk and MA student Kaidi Meus.</p>
<p>Media and Communications</p>	<p>PI UK Professor Sonia Livingstone at the London School of Economics and Political Science, UK. The UK team included Mariya Stoilova and PhD candidate Jo Lahlum Hortman.</p>
	<p>PI Romania Professor Oana Benga at the Babes-Bolyai Univ., Cluj-Napoca, Romania. The Romanian team included Oana Negru, Ionut Mone, Georgiana Susa-Erdogan, Iulia Domocus, Flavia Medrea.</p>
	<p>PI Girona, Spain Professor Moises Esteban-Guitart from the University of Girona, Catalonia/Spain. The Girona team included Sara Malo, Antonio Membrive Ruiz.</p>
	<p>PI Barcelona, Spain Associate Professor Raquel Miño-Puigcercós from the University of Barcelona, Catalonia/Spain. The Barcelona team included Judith Jacovkis, Gustavo Herrera, Pablo Rivera, Paula Lozano Mulet, Xavier Giro, Carlota Rodríguez Silva.</p>
	<p>PI Poland Assistant Professor Bogumiła Mateja-Jaworska from the Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan, Poland. The Polish team also included researcher Marta Skowronska.</p>

Overview of the research design

PlatFAMs' methodology is an innovative and participatory design, where grandparents, parents, and children and youth from more than 100 families in six European countries were included in the data collection. Aiming at recruiting diverse families, we included families with same-sex parents, families with different-gender parents, single parent families, divorced families, blended families, families with neurodiverse members, immigrant and transnational families, and other three generation families where the interviewees have different kinds of relationships to each other.

The 313 individual interviews included a number of visual cues, as well as methods to invite the interviewees to reflect about their use and experiences with the rather abstract platform technology in the form of apps and algorithms. Specifically, interviewees were shown a myriad of app logos under various headings such as communication, gaming, health, streaming, banking, shopping, and transportation.

The themes of the individual interviews circled around these app- and platform logos, focusing on how the interviewee used and navigated the platforms in family contexts. The temporal aspect was included by asking the interviewee to place the logos of their 'digital platform life' according to past, present and future. The interview was designed to dig deep into aspects like intimacy, care, conflicts and discussions, privacy, sharing online, algorithms, temporal changes in the family and platform use, platforms' role in society in the future.

Following the individual interviews, ten families (two from each country) were selected for family (group) interviews. The interview guide for the family interviews was specifically designed to target media generations and childhood memories of communication and media use, by inviting all family members to bring an item or a photo – or just a memory – of something that they felt was particular to the media use in their own childhood/youth. In the second half of the interview, the family was invited to design the perfect app for their family. They were asked to do this by identifying, first, activities they would like to be able to do using an app in the future, and second, identifying features an app would need to have to do these activities. Subsequently, they were asked to reflect on whether there were any activities they would prefer to keep offline.

Data management and ethical considerations

The consortium developed a data management plan. While researchers from all participating countries must oblige by the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) law, some the rules and regulations regarding data management vary across consortium countries. Therefore, each consortium further developed the necessary documentation and followed the procedures necessary according to the local regulations. More information about this can be found in the country specific sections below.

In addition to data management, the teams developed a joint understanding of the ethical aspects of the project.

The project's original commitment to depositing anonymized data in CESSDA has been reconsidered. Fully anonymizing relational family data would compromise its utility. Instead, we will deposit data in a secure, access-controlled repository, in line with FAIR principles and funder requirements. The DMP detailing strategies for de-identification, metadata standards, access restrictions, and long-term preservation protocols is currently being updated.

In the project, we interviewed informants that required various ethical considerations. First, informants' age varied greatly and particularly data collection from the youngest participants required adjustments. Several interviews were conducted in a different language either by the interviewer or with an interpreter (a non-participating family member or a research assistant). Interviews with children were adapted based on their age - offering additional explanations, keeping questions shorter, and keeping the overall interview shorter (by asking fewer prompts). Children who preferred their parent(s) to be present during the interview were allowed to do so. In some cases the consenting parent were invited into the conversation during the interview to comment. In other cases, parents were silent onlookers, and it is hard to say whether their presence influenced the data in any way.

Recruitment of sample

The project applied a strategy of obtaining a sample of interviewees that included a variety of genders, ages, educational and ethnic backgrounds, as well as residency in different degrees of urbanisation. We also aimed to reach different types of families, both two-parent households as well as 'blended' families, one parent households etc. Different strategies were applied, where both people from the grandparent and the parent generation could act as 'anchor generation' and recruit the rest of the family.

The sample of informants are described briefly in the country specific sections, and more precisely in Appendix 2: "Sample characteristics by country".

T1 Interview guide: Individual interviews

Development

The interview guide was developed as a collaborative process between the five original participating countries in the PlatFAMs project (Estonia, Romania, Spain, the United Kingdom, and Norway, respectively). The first draft of the interview guide was initially discussed in plenary group meetings, and later discussed in a dedicated task force for the development of the interview guide consisting of one to two project members from each country.

After the first version of the interview guide was finalized, all five countries tested the guide by conducting pilot interviews. Subsequently, the interview guide was discussed and improved based on identified shortcomings.

As Poland joined the PlatFAMs group later, they adapted the existing interview guide to national contexts.

Themes

The themes of the final interview guide were organized in three parts.

1. *Your family* – the interviewee was asked to describe their family members – who lives in your household, who are other relatives? How would you describe your family?
2. *Navigation: The digital platforms of family life* – The interviewees were shown a wide array of digital platforms exemplified by pictures of app logos organized in 13 categories: school and learning, care, health and training, economy, shopping, travel and transport, streaming and entertainment, content, communication and messaging, social networks and media, gaming/games, parental control and surveillance, genealogy, cloud storage. In total, the 13 categories included more than 100 different logos. Using the logos as examples, the interviewee was asked to describe their use and experiences with the platform, as well as relational aspects of the digital platforms used *for*, *with* or *in* the family. The temporal aspect was included by asking the interviewee to place the logos of their ‘digital platform life’ according to past, present and future. The interviewer would take photos of the platform logos on the table before and after it had been organized temporally. The logos are included in appendix 1.
3. *Negotiation and futuremaking: Relational and temporal aspects of digital platforms* – the third part was designed to dig deeper into aspects like intimacy, care, conflicts and discussions, privacy, sharing online, algorithms, temporal changes in the family and platform use, platforms’ role in society in the future.

Visual cues for individual interviews (T1): Illustration of interview where an informant have picked out their preferred and used app logos from the envelopes with visual representations of digital platforms.

T2 Interview guide: Family interviews

The interview guide for the second round of interviews was specifically designed to target focus group interviews with participating families.

The first part of the interview invited all family members to bring an item or a photo – or just a memory – of something that they felt was particular to their media use at the age of the child/youth who participated in the interview. The interview guide followed up on this by including questions about their ‘Media generation’ - thinking of themselves as representatives of a social generation with their particular media habits and experiences from their childhood and youth. This part of the interview aimed at capturing the family dynamics between generations, focusing on how they saw the differences between the generations, and what they would advise or teach the other generations based on their experiences from media use of their time.

The second part of the family interview was an invitation to develop the “perfect app” for their family. Participants were asked to 1) identify activities that they liked to do together, and 2) discuss what type of app they would need to be able to do these activities, and 3) reflect on what features the app needed to have to achieve this. See appendix 1 for interview guides and data collection materials.

Participatory methods: Informants prepared for the family interview by bringing ‘media generation objects’ into the conversation.

Country specific descriptions of ethics, recruitment, sample, data collection and transcription

Estonia

Authors: Signe Opermann, Maris Männiste, Veronika Kalmus

Recruitment

This qualitative study primarily employed purposive sampling to identify families in which all three generational members had at least some experience using digital platforms. To recruit participants, members of the research team utilized their extended social networks. Consequently, the sample can also be considered a convenience sample. However, not all participating families were personally known to the researchers; some were recommended by contacts within the social network - i.e., acquaintances of acquaintances - whom the researchers did not know directly.

In most cases (though not exclusively), we approached families through the middle generation, typically peers of the researchers. Sometimes, the middle-generation participant recommended their spouse or partner, sometimes they participated themselves, and they also facilitated contact with their children and their own parents or in-laws, inviting them to take part in the study.

During recruitment, we sent each family a brief written introduction outlining the study's aims. The goal was to identify families in which members from all three generations were at least moderately digitally active and had independent experience using digital platforms.

From the outset of recruitment, families were informed that participation would involve two phases, and they were asked to be prepared for this. All 11 families agreed to take part in both phases. When the project consortium later decided that fewer families - at least two per country - would participate in the second phase (the family group interview), we reviewed the profiles of the families recruited in phase one, taking into account any changes in their living arrangements.

The main consideration was whether the family members could easily gather in the same place at the same time for a group interview. We also reflected on their willingness, as observed during the first-phase interviews, to engage in a collaborative creative task - namely, designing an "ideal platform" for their family and discussing it together. Based on this internal evaluation, two families were selected to participate in the second phase of the study. The same family members who participated in the first phase of the study also took part in the second phase. No new individuals from these two families were recruited, nor did any express interest in joining at that stage.

The middle-generation representatives (Gen2) from 10 families were recruited directly by members of the research team. One participant from the grandparent generation (Gen1) was recruited through the mother of a research team member, as the participant was her acquaintance. This grandmother then recruited her daughter-in-law and grandchild to join the study, forming a complete three-generation family unit. One family was recruited through the grandparent generation (Gen 1) as in that particular case we aimed to increase the balance of male-female participants in the interviews. Thus, it was first important to confirm the grandfathers (Gen 1) to participate and after that other family members from Gen 2 and Gen 3 were approached.

Country specific ethical considerations

During participant recruitment, we took care to avoid collecting excessive personal data. To ensure privacy from the outset, the researcher responsible for recruiting each family assigned a pseudonym - typically a common Estonian surname - and did not disclose the participants' identities, even within the research team. Personal data were recorded only on the informed consent forms signed by the participants. These forms, when signed electronically, were encrypted and securely stored by the designated data manager in Estonia, following the procedures outlined in the data management plan.

Additionally, we shortened some interview audio recordings when participants shared highly personal stories or details that were not relevant to the study's objectives. All audio recordings - including the shortened ones - were transcribed and edited by a professional transcriber whose contract with the university included an obligation of confidentiality. Each transcript was then pseudonymized by the researcher who conducted the interview. This involved replacing all names, place names, and other identifiable details mentioned in the original recordings.

Only after this thorough editing and pseudonymization process were the transcripts made available to the research team for analysis. Prior to recruitment and data collection, the team developed a detailed internal document outlining all procedures to ensure that researchers could carry out their work in full compliance with ethical and data protection standards.

Sample of informants

A total of 11 families from Estonia participated in the study, with three individuals from each generational group, resulting in a sample of 33 participants. Of these, 18 were female and 15 male.

In the oldest generation (Gen1), there were 9 female and 2 male participants; in the middle generation (Gen2), there were 6 female and 5 male participants. Among the youngest generation (Gen3), 3 girls and 8 boys took part. The oldest participant was 75 years old at the time of the first phase of the study, and the youngest was 9. The age range for Gen1 was 47–75 years, for Gen2 29–55 years, and for Gen3 9–17 years. Ten families lived in Estonia, while one transnational family had its Gen2 and Gen3 members residing in a Scandinavian country, with the Gen1 members living in Estonia. Thirteen participants lived in larger cities (including the capital), seven in smaller towns, and thirteen in rural areas. One blended family had same-sex parents (Gen2); one was a single-parent family (mother, Gen2).

Of the 33 participants, ten had completed higher education, eleven had secondary or vocational education, and twelve had either completed or were in the process of completing basic education (among them 11 participating children aged between 9 and 17).

Women were notably overrepresented in the grandparent generation (Gen1), with only two grandfathers participating. In some families, only the grandmother was present, making it impossible to recruit a male participant from that generation.

Most participants belonged to the ethnic majority.

The majority of families were classified as belonging to the middle SES status group, with a few families (or individual generational members) falling into the lower SES category (lower-middle or lower class), and a small number into the higher SES category (upper-middle class).

The sample was unbalanced, as compared to the country statistics, with regard to gender in Gen1 and Gen3 (while the sample as a whole was balanced) and ethnicity (the proportion of the ethnic minority is larger in the population).

Interviews

Location, Time use and time period of interviews

The individual interviews (T1) were carried out between November 26, 2023 and May 28, 2024. The family interviews (T2) were carried out in December, 2024.

The interviews were conducted by the members of the Estonian research team: Veronika Kalmus, Andra Siibak, Signe Opermann, Maris Männiste, Marit Napp, and a Master's student Kaidi Meus whose MA thesis was supervised by Veronika Kalmus and Andra Siibak.

The individual interviews were conducted in the participants' and interviewers' native language (Estonian) and lasted approximately 60 minutes on average, while one of the family interviews lasted around 1.5 hours and the second around 2,5 hours.

In the first phase of the study, 29 interviews were conducted in person, while 4 were carried out online using video conferencing platforms such as Zoom. 11 interviews took place in the participants' homes; the remaining interviews were held in public locations such as university, library, or similar venues.

In the second phase, both family interviews were conducted in person. All family members gathered in the same location - such as the grandparents' house - for the group interview.

Recording, technical solutions, transcriptions

All interviews were audio-recorded (by using a dictaphone, smartphone or Zoom) and transcribed (by a professional transcriber contracted by the university), after which the transcripts were pseudonymized manually by the research team members.

Anonymity, de-personalisation of interviews

All participants in the study were assured confidentiality as it was documented in the informed consent form. Only family members who also took part in the study were aware of each other's identities. From the recruitment stage onward, the research team used pseudonyms when referring to participants within the research group, the consortium, and in publications. This ensured that even members of the research team did not know the names or other personal data of families or individuals they had not personally recruited or interviewed. The pseudonyms were selected from the most common Estonian surnames. If participants or their acquaintances were mentioned by first name during interviews, these names were also replaced with pseudonyms; the names of locations, schools or companies were replaced with letters (e.g., school X, village Y).

Data collected through interviews inevitably contain a significant amount of personal information, most typically in an unstructured form. As a result, complete and irreversible anonymisation of the whole dataset is not feasible. To protect participants' privacy and confidentiality, we employed a pseudonymisation strategy. The data, including pseudonymised interview transcripts, are not shared outside the research team or published (made public) under any circumstances.

Storage of data

The data collected throughout the project are stored securely at the University of Tartu OwnCloud cloud service as well as on a separate external hard drive. Data on the external hard drive has been updated regularly.

All the researchers have full access to the OwnCloud. For a short period of time also the employed transcriber (with whom we have a contract that includes a confidentiality obligation) also had access to the audio files through a separate OwnCloud folder.

The signed informed consents are stored only on an external hard drive, and the paper copies are kept at the university, in a locked drawer in a locked office room. All digitally kept informed consents are encrypted using Estonia's national software assigned for this purpose and accessible only for the researcher who conducted the interview and for the project leader.

The documents containing personal data will be stored for no longer than five years. All the audio files were deleted when the transcriptions of the interviews were controlled and anonymised.

All activities involving the data collection and storage are in accordance with the agreement jointly signed within the consortium, and we have no additional documents to upload.

Spain

Authors: Raquel Miño-Puigcercos, Moises Guitart-Esteban

Recruitment of interviewees

The recruitment of the Spanish sample was purposive and followed two strategies, based on availability, accessibility and relevance. First, we contacted parents with children attending schools from different geographical areas and grade levels. Through this approach, the parent generation acted as “anchor generation” to recruit the rest of the family. This strategy facilitated the inclusion of families from diverse social classes, composed by three generations, with at least one child aged between 8 and 17 years.

The second strategy sought to ensure diversity within the sample, by considering ethnic backgrounds and specially inviting monomarental and homoparental families. To achieve this, we relied on professional, institutional and personal networks, aiming to better represent the heterogeneity of families in Spain.

The recruitment of the two families for the T2 interviews was also intentional. We selected families with a high level of reflexivity around digital platforms, as identified in the T1 interviews. One case was a middle-class family from Girona with two 9-year-old daughters, and the other was a working-class family from Barcelona with an 11-year-old non-binary child.

The main sources for recruitment were professional and personal networks. Parents from different public, private and charter schools in Barcelona and Girona were contacted. In addition, students from the University of Barcelona invited their families to participate. Finally, families closed to the researchers’ personal networks were reached. All contacts were made by email or phone.

Country specific ethical considerations

The Spanish team submitted the project to the Bioethics Committee of the University of Barcelona and the Research Ethics and Biosecurity Committee from the University of Girona before data collection. The Committee of the University of Barcelona suggested some modifications, which were incorporated before obtaining a favorable dictamen on November 27th, 2023. The documentation was reviewed by the Institutional Review Board IRB00003099, which assigned the project code CER112331. The University of Girona Committee approved the project on October 23rd, 2023, under the code CEBRU0032-23.

Recommendations mainly concerned data protection and data storage, as well as the structure of the consent form, which was adapted to standard formulations for Spanish participants.

All interviews were conducted without major difficulties, and all the participants signed informed consent forms. The only exception was a grandmother from Fam04, who initially agreed but ultimately did not participate due to health issues.

Sample

The Spanish sample included 63 individuals, reflecting diversity in gender, age, social class, ethnic background and rural/urban residence. Monomarental and homoparental families were also included, ensuring representation beyond traditional family structures. Middle-class families were slightly overrepresented compared to official statistics in Spain.

Generations

Of the 20 families, 19 were represented by three generations and 1 could not include the grandparent generation. Three families included 2 children in the interviews, and one family included the grandparent and the grandmother.

Age and gender

Participants ranged from 8 to 87 years old. The youngest grandparent was 57 and the oldest 87. The parent generation span was from 41 to 57 (median=41). The youngest child was 8 and the oldest 16. Among the interviewees, there were 37 woman/girls, 26 man/boys and 1 non-binary child.

Ethnic/minority background

Seven families (35%) included members with migrant background or with a member of the grandparents and/or parents' generations with a minority ethnic background. In total, 4 grandparents, 6 parents and 3 children define themselves as migrants. Two grandparents lived abroad and, therefore, their interviews were conducted online. This distribution reflects Spanish' ethnic composition.

Area of residence

The families of the sample lived in the capital cities of Barcelona or Girona (32%), in other cities (45,3%), and in rural areas (21,9%). Two grandparents resided abroad, in Colombia and Chile.

Educational level of parents and grandparents

Educational attainment in Spain is slightly below the OECD average (63% of adults have completed upper secondary education and 39,9% have completed higher education). Among the grandparents of the sample, 13 from 19 had completed upper secondary school (68%, 2 missing information) and 16 parents had completed higher education (80%). Therefore, this group is overrepresented, especially in the parents' generation.

Family structure

Most families of the sample were nuclear (15), while 3 were monoparental, reflecting the Spanish population (24%). The sample also included 2 homoparental families.

Regarding the number of children, most families (n= 12, 66,7%) had two children, 4 families had one child and 2 had three or more children (2 missing information).

The sample consisted of the following dyads: 5 father-son, 5 father-daughter, 5 mother-daughter, 4 mother-son, and 1 mother-non-binary dyad.

Interviews

The interviews from Barcelona were conducted by Paula Lozano, Raquel Miño, Gustavo Herrera, Judith Jacovkis and Lluís Parcerisa and the interviews from Girona by Antonio Membrive, Mariana Largo and Sara Malo.

Time period: January – September 2024. The pilot interview was conducted in January 2024. The rest of the interviews took place between May and September 2024.

The length of the interviews: Varied from 40 minutes to up to 2 hours.

Location: Most interviews with parents and children were conducted at the participants' homes, often simultaneously by different researchers. Grandparents were usually interviewed at their own homes, though in some cases in the parents' homes. Four interviews took place in in cafés and bars. Eight were conducted online (two due to family needs, and two because the grandparents lived abroad).

All interviews were transcribed using Microsoft Office, ensuring that both audios and transcripts were stored in the project SharePoint folder, in accordance with the Data Management Plan. Transcriptions were manually checked by research assistants.

All transcripts were de-individualized by replacing personal names. Families were coded as "Fam01, Fam02, Fam03..." and pseudonyms were assigned to each family member.

The Spanish data was stored at the University of Barcelona project SharePoint folder, in accordance with the Bioethics Commission regulations.

Poland

Author: Bogumiła Mateja-Jaworska

Recruitment

Since Poland joined the project at a later stage and the research team was relatively small (two researchers), it was agreed that only 30 interviews in 10 families would be conducted in this country (ultimately, however, it was possible to recruit 11 families and carry out 33 interviews). In line with the agreements within the research consortium, special attention was paid during recruitment to ensuring that the families participating in the study would be as diverse as possible, particularly in terms of such social variables as: place of residence (large city, small town, village), level of education and standard of living (SES), gender, ethnic background, and diversity of family situations (transnational families, families after separation/divorce, heterosexual and homosexual families). Taking into account the specific characteristics of family life structures in Poland (Census 2021[1]), it was assumed that the sample should include at least:

1. one refugee family from Ukraine;
2. one non-heterosexual family;
3. one transnational family (in which one or two of the participants spend a significant part of the year abroad);
4. at least two families in which the parents are divorced, separated, or single parents;
5. at least two families living in rural areas;
6. at least two families living in a town;
7. at least seven individuals (out of the 20 adult participants) with primary, vocational, or secondary education; in addition, at least one participant with higher education should have a background in computer science or work in the IT sector;
8. efforts would be made to balance the number of women and men in the sample;
9. efforts would be made to balance the number of younger children (aged 8–12) and teenagers (aged 13–18).

Initially, the recruitment strategy aimed to begin with different generations (grandparents, parents, children). However, this approach proved to be rather ineffective, especially when starting with children. Beginning with the oldest generation was successful only in the case of Family 8 (the first recruited participant was GEN1, who subsequently encouraged her daughter and grandson to take part in the study). In all other cases, it was always the parent generation (GEN2) that independently identified which members of the grandparent generation (GEN1) and the child generation (GEN3) they considered to be part of the family and with whom interviews could or should be conducted.

In many cases, the researchers tried to negotiate the proposed participants in order to maintain an appropriate gender balance in the sample (for example, by asking whether it would be possible to speak with the grandfather rather than the grandmother). Nevertheless, such suggestions were usually final, which explains both the limited participation of grandparents in the sample and the predominance of blood-related family members — respondents almost always indicated their biological parent rather than a parent-in-law.

When recruiting families for T2, it was assumed that, in addition to those who had already participated in the interviews, other family members who expressed interest (e.g., siblings, the second parent, or the other grandparent) could optionally be invited to join the meeting. In selecting the two families for the second stage of the study, several factors were taken into account: that they

should be reflective and willing to engage in a longer conversation (based on the experiences from T1); that it would be possible to gather all three generations in one place located no more than two hours by train from the researchers' place of residence; and that the families would differ from each other in terms of:

- their attitudes toward media and digital platforms (based on knowledge from the first round of research – a more relaxed versus a more restrictive approach to media use),
- their socio-economic position (a less affluent versus a more affluent family),
- their family structure (a traditional versus a patchwork family).

Based on these criteria, Family 1 and Family 6 participated in T2. In the latter case, in addition to the grandfather (from T1), the grandmother also agreed to take part in the second round – she had already been indicated by GEN2 in the first round as a potential respondent.

Despite applying various recruitment strategies, the most effective approach turned out to be the use of personal connections to identify participants with the socio-demographic characteristics outlined above. In one case, respondents were recruited from a university database created for an earlier research project (several years ago, these respondents had given their consent to be contacted in the event of new academic research initiatives on AMU).

Country specific ethical considerations

The project, research instruments, and sampling procedure were submitted to the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Sociology at Adam Mickiewicz University. After incorporating the Committee's comments (including, among others, adding a space for the signatures of underage respondents on the consent form in addition to that of the adult participant, and clarifying the process of adapting the instrument to the Polish context), the study's methodology received a positive recommendation from the Committee.

Consent form: All participants (and, in the case of underage respondents, their legal guardians) completed an informed consent form prior to participation in the study. Each family also received an information sheet about the research project, outlining potential difficulties related to participation and indicating the contact persons to whom any concerns about irregularities during the study could be reported.

As a token of appreciation for their participation, respondents received prepaid cards for their discretionary use.

Adaptation for respondents with special needs: For the youngest participants (ages 9–11) and for an older, ill respondent, every effort was made to ensure that interviews did not exceed one hour in duration (ranging from 30 to 60 minutes).

Language considerations: In the case of the refugee family from Ukraine, the eldest respondent did not speak Polish. A friend of this family (of Gen2), who was proficient in both Polish and Ukrainian, was engaged as an interpreter.

Sample

The study included 33 respondents in T1 and 7 in T2 (6 from T1 and 1 new) across 11 families. Although it was initially planned to recruit 10 families, due to the hospitalization of a member of one family, an additional family was recruited. However, the interview with this family member was conducted somewhat later; thus, the final sample consisted of 11 three-generation families.

Taking into account the criteria outlined below, the sample reflects relatively well the structure of families in central and western Poland. Nevertheless, it is skewed primarily by a gender imbalance (overrepresentation of women) and a slightly higher proportion of parents with higher education than in the general population. The sample also lacks a family with a single parent raising children. According to the 2021 national census, this internally diverse category (“single mothers with children” and “single fathers with children,” including divorced parents, widows/widowers, and single parents) accounts for approximately 24% of all families in Poland.

Generations

In all recruited families, it was possible to conduct interviews with representatives of each of the three generations.

Age

Respondents within each generation were broadly similar in age. Grandparents were generally around 70 years old (with the exception of Gen1 from Ukraine, aged 59). Parents had an average age of 41.2 (the youngest being Gen2 from Ukraine, aged 34). Among the children (average age 12.8), an effort was made to balance younger children (9–12 years; 6 participants) and teenagers (13–18 years; 5 participants).

Gender

Despite best efforts, it was not possible to achieve a gender balance in the sample. This imbalance was primarily due to the overrepresentation of women in the oldest generation. Several factors contributed to this skew: men’s reluctance to participate in research, the withdrawal of (especially older) men from family matters (in some cases it was made explicit that family relations were considered the domain of women, and therefore women were seen as the appropriate participants), as well as war (the refugee family), and the shorter life expectancy of men in Poland (in several families the grandfathers were deceased – men’s life expectancy in Poland is seven years shorter than that of women).

Ethnicity

Despite ongoing social changes, Polish society remains largely ethnically homogeneous, particularly outside major cities. A significant development in recent years, however, has been the influx of labor migrants and, more recently, war refugees from Ukraine – mostly women with children. Poland also has a long tradition of emigration; especially after EU accession in 2004, it became increasingly common to form transnational families in which one parent, the whole family, or a grandparent moved abroad for work, particularly to Germany, the UK, Ireland, or Norway. Both of these family situations were reflected in the sample.

Education

The oldest generation was highly diverse in terms of educational attainment (ranging from primary, vocational, and secondary to higher education), reflecting the general educational structure of older

adults in Poland. Among the parent generation, those with higher education were somewhat overrepresented, while no participants with vocational education were included.

Urban/rural

Although the modest number of recruited families and the need to meet multiple criteria did not allow the proportions of large-city, small-town, and rural families to mirror those of the overall population in Poland, families were recruited from different types of localities, ensuring diversity (e.g., a village with limited transport connections, a commuter village near a large city, and a village close to a small town). However, compared to data from the 2021 national census, the sample should have included more rural families (42% of all families with children in Poland live in rural areas). For organizational reasons, all respondents were recruited from central and western Poland; thus, the eastern regions of the country were not represented in the sample.

Interviews

Time period of interviews: Due to Poland's later accession to the PlatFams project, the T1 interviews were conducted between September 2024 and January 2025 (with the final interview, delayed due to the respondent's hospitalization, carried out in March 2025). The group interviews within T2 were conducted in February and March 2025.

Who conducted interviews? The interviews were conducted by Bogumiła Mateja-Jaworska (27 IDI during T1 and 2 during T2) and Marta Skowronska (6 IDI).

Duration: The duration of the interviews ranged from 30 minutes (in the case of an elderly respondent in poor health) to nearly 3 hours. Interviews with representatives of the grandparent generation lasted between 30 minutes and 1 hour 45 minutes. Those with the children's generation typically took approximately 1 hour in the case of younger children and up to 1 hour 50 minutes with older teenagers. The longest sessions were recorded with the parent generation, varying from approximately 90 minutes to almost 3 hours.

Location: Most interviews were conducted in the interviewees' homes (27 IDI in T1 and 2 FGi in T2), and the grandparent was occasionally interviewed in the Gen2 home (1 out of 11 grandparents, and both cases in T2).

Of the remaining 6 interviews, 3 were conducted at AMU (due to the family's difficult housing conditions), 2 in cafés (one with a grandparent and one with a teenage respondent), and 1 at the workplace of a Gen2 participant.

A total of 28 interviews were conducted entirely face-to-face (including all with the grandparent generation), while 3 took place exclusively online (2 of these with members of transnational families who were abroad at the time). In 2 cases (including the longest interview, which lasted almost 3 hours in total), the sessions began during a home visit but, for organizational reasons (a scheduled appointment of the respondent, a train departure), were completed online the following day.

The family interviews within T2 were conducted face-to-face in the homes of Gen2 participants and lasted just over two hours.

All interviews were transcribed using the Autotekst tool within Educloud, which employs the NB Whisper solution to convert audio recordings into Polish text. The Autotekst AI transcription software

operates offline and is not connected to the internet. Each transcript was subsequently verified and corrected manually by a research assistant to ensure accuracy.

All transcripts were anonymised through the replacement of personal names, place names, and other identifying details. Within each family, any personal names occurring across multiple interviews were assigned the same pseudonym to maintain internal consistency. Vocational details requiring anonymisation were replaced with alternative occupations, selected to reflect a comparable level of education and socio-economic status.

All place names that could serve as identifiers were substituted with descriptive labels, retaining essential contextual information while generalising to a broader geographical area. For example, the city of Poznań was replaced with “[large city in central-western Poland],” and Wyszyny was replaced with “[rural area in the northern part of Greater Poland].”

All alterations were documented in family-specific files stored in the family folders on a secure, Poland-specific Educloud server, together with the audio recordings and the non-anonymised transcripts.

Additional information for Poland

During the translation and adaptation of the T1 interview guide to the Polish context, two modifications were introduced:

1. Platform logos: Logos of platforms unavailable to Polish users were removed, and instead, logos of platforms and applications particularly popular among Polish users were added. The selection was based on data on Polish internet users published in 2024 by PBI (Polskie Badania Internetu) as well as up-to-date download statistics from Google Play and the App Store across relevant categories.
2. Reduction of thematic areas: Following feedback from consortium members that interviews occasionally exceeded the planned 90 minutes, the number of areas was reduced from 13 to 11. Categories that respondents often found difficult to distinguish—namely messengers, social media, and content platforms (like TikTok)—were merged into one broader subset. In addition, follow-up questions focused primarily on domains related to communication, health, education, and entertainment, while less attention was given to areas such as commerce and banking.

[1] <https://stat.gov.pl/spisy-powszechne/nsp-2021/nsp-2021-wyniki-ostateczne/rodziny-w-polsce-w-swietle-wynikow-nsp-2021,7,2.html> (published in 12.2023)

Romania

Author: Oana Benga, Georgiana Erdogan

Recruitment

For the recruitment of the Romanian sample, we targeted families with at least one child aged 8-17 and all three generational members having some experience using digital platforms. The team used several recruitment strategies: snowballing from personal contacts and from participants, contacting organizations working with families and/or seniors, advertising on social media (staff profiles and research networks). Most participants were ultimately sourced via extended personal and professional networks, thus the resulting sample was a convenience one. Out of the 22 families involved in the project, 5 were recruited via a participant and 1 via a senior day center. The resulting sample was relatively diverse in terms of geographical areas (9 families from Cluj, the rest from other regions in Transylvania, i.e. Maramures, Alba, Hunedoara), educational level and socio-demographic characteristics.

For the T2 interviews, two families were selected, based on their high level of reflexivity and their availability (and willingness) to gather for a group interview, as well as to engage in the collaborative task.

In most cases, families were approached through the middle (parent) generation, who facilitated further contact with children and grandparent generations, inviting them to take part in the study. Two participants from the grandparent generation were directly contacted from a research member team and served as a personal contact hub for reaching other family members.

Country specific ethical considerations

The Romanian team submitted the project description, the parental consent form for minors, and the informed consent form to the Scientific Council for Ethical Approval of Babeş-Bolyai University prior to data collection. The Committee recommended that the procedures for data storage and anonymization be described in detail. We incorporated this recommendation and obtained ethical approval under reference number 868/10.11.2023. The raw data collected within the study were stored on a secured computer with no internet connection at Babeş-Bolyai University and were not shared with consortium members from other countries. The data shared with consortium members were pseudonymized and edited according to specific criteria. Any personal information/data that could have led to the identification of the individual who generated the data (e.g., name, place of residence) were removed.

Sample

The sample consisted of 66 participants: 22 children (9 boys, 40.9%; M = 11.41 years, SD = 2.82, age range 8-16 years), 22 parents (2 men, 9.1%; M = 39.65 years, SD = 5.73, age range 27-50 years), and 22 grandparents (4 men, 18.2%; M = 66.13 years, SD = 6.28, 57-78 years). In terms of ethnicity, most of the participants (N= 65) belonged to the ethnic majority. 13 grandparents, 14 children, and 14 parents lived in urban settings, whereas 9 grandparents, 8 children, and 8 parents lived in rural settings. Overall, 32.80% of the participants lived in a large city, 36.10% in a small town and 31.10% in rural areas. Among the grandparent generation, 33.35 % had higher education, 14.3% had

incomplete university education, 38.1% had between 10-13 years of education, while 14.3% had between 7-9 years of education. Among the parent generation, 68.2 % had higher education, 9.1% had incomplete university education, while 22.7% had between 10-13 years of education. The second generation families were either divorced or one parent families in 18.2% cases; the rest of 81.8% were two-parent heterosexual couples. Most families included one or two children (95.5%), and only one family included four children.

The sample was unbalanced in terms of gender (particularly for Gen1 and Gen2) and ethnicity.

Interviews

Time period of interviews: The individual interviews (T1) were carried out between March and June, 2024. The family interviews (T2) were carried out in December, 2024.

Who conducted interviews? The interviews were conducted by the members of the Romanian research team: Flavia Medrea, Iulia Mihaela Bunea (Domocus), Ionut-Sergiu Mone.

Duration: The individual interviews were conducted in the participants' and interviewers' native language (Romanian) and lasted from 50 minutes to up to 3 hours. The family interviews lasted 2h 45min and 1h 25min, respectively.

Location: All interviews were conducted in person. Most interviews with parents and children were conducted in the participants' homes, often simultaneously by different researchers (12 families; n=24 interviews). For 7 families, Gen2 and Gen3 interviews (n=14 interviews) took place at Babes-Bolyai University. In the case of 3 families, parents and children were interviewed in grandparents' home (n=6 interviews). Grandparents were interviewed in their own homes (10), in the parents' homes (8), at the Day Senior Center (1) or at Babes-Bolyai University (3). In the second phase, both family interviews were conducted in person. All family members gathered in the same location - at the parents' house (family 1) and at Babes-Bolyai University (family 2).

All interviews were audio-recorded (by using a dictaphone or smartphone) and transcribed using Autotekst tool within Educloud, which employs the NB Whisper solution to convert audio recordings into Romanian. This software operates offline and is not connected to the internet. Each transcript was subsequently verified and corrected manually by a research assistant to ensure accuracy. One interview (Gen1) had to be excluded due to data loss caused by a technical issue during audio recording.

All interviews were checked and anonymized, removing manually all personal details (e.g., names of people, places, other identifying details) by the research team members. All families were given a specific family name pseudonym. The pseudonyms were selected from the most common Romanian surnames.

The data collected throughout the project were stored securely at Babes-Bolyai University (a protected folder on a computer with no internet connection), in accordance with the Scientific Council for Ethical Approval of Babeş-Bolyai University.

UK - England

Author: Mariya Stoilova, London School of economics

Recruitment of interviewees

For the recruitment of the UK sample, the team used several methods – snowballing from personal contacts and from participants, contacting an organisation working with families, putting adverts on social media (staff profiles and research networks on Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter), sharing information via a research-based mailing list for parents, distributing information leaflets in public libraries. The most productive method yielding the large majority of participants was snowballing from personal contacts (n=15 families recruited). A small number of families were also recruited via social media (n=4), the mailing list (n=1) and via a participant (n=1).

The selection of the Phase II families was based on the availability of the three generations and their ability to meet in person with the researcher, as well as families or members who were underrepresented in the research (men, lower SES, lower use of platforms, neurodiversity, outside London, diversity in the ways that they used platforms).

Most of the families were recruited via the mother (n=6, via personal contact, mailing list, social media), the grandmother (n=5, via personal contact or social media) or another family member who did not take part in the research (aunt/uncle or non-participating parent; n=5 via personal contact or another participant). A smaller number were recruited via the father (n=3, via personal contact or social media) or the grandfather (n=2, personal contact).

Country specific ethical considerations

The project received approval from the Research Ethics Committee at the London School of Economics and Political Science (REC ref. 184400). All researchers in this study underwent an Enhanced DBS Check with a check against the Children's Barred List to ensure they are safe to work with children.

Several interviews were conducted in a different language either by the interviewer or with an interpreter (a non-participating family member or a research assistant). Interviews with children were adapted based on their age - offering additional explanations, keeping questions shorter, and keeping the overall interview shorter (by asking fewer prompts).

Sample

The sample consisted of 64 participants equally split between male and female (32 female and 32 male). There were no participants who identified with any other gender. The participant ages ranged from 7.5 to 84 years, with an average age of 43. In terms of ethnicity, over a third of the participants (n=27) were from non-majority backgrounds (i.e., not White British). Regarding area of residence, 34 participants were from the capital or a capital city (about half), three lived in a city, 13 were from a

town, and 14 lived in villages or rural areas. Socioeconomic status (SES) was also diverse: 20 participants had low SES, 20 had medium, and 24 had high SES.

The UK sample is diverse and overall balanced in terms of age, gender, and SES. It is more ethnically diverse than the UK average, which may enrich insights, particularly regarding marginalised or underrepresented perspectives. The sample is reasonably balanced in terms of area of residence but slightly over-represents those in capital cities.

Interviews

Phase I of the fieldwork was conducted between January and December 2024, Phase II was conducted in December 2024. The interviews were conducted by the team members - Sonia Livingstone and Mariya Stoilova

The interviews lasted between 39 and 116 minutes, with an average length of 70 minutes, amounting to a total of 4,451 minutes of recorded material.

Of the total, 60 interviews were conducted face to face and 4 interviews were conducted online (3 with grandparents living abroad and one with a grandparent living in a different city). The majority of the interviews were conducted in the participants home, 9 were conducted elsewhere (mostly the home of another family member).

All the interviews were recorded via sound recording equipment and transferred to a protected folder LSE's OneDrive as soon as possible.

Transcripts were produced through a dedicated research software (Autotekst) which is GDPR-compliant and hosted on the server of the University of Oslo. The automated transcriptions were checked and corrected by a research assistant.

All interviews were carefully checked and anonymised removing all personal details such as names of people, places, employers, etc.

All the interviews were stored on a protected folder on LSE's OneDrive. Personally identifiable data (e.g., consent forms) were stored separately from research data.

Norway

Authors: Kristinn Hegna, Maja Nordtug

Recruitment

Several strategies to recruit participants were applied. At the outset, we aimed to recruit both the grandparents as well as from the children and ask them to recruit the rest of the family. Our first strategy was to start with the grandparents, and several senior citizens were recruited through meetings and presentations of the PlatFAMs project for the organization Seniornett. This is an organization with a well-developed network of local groups that offer information and competence to seniors in use of digital technology. We approached two local groups and through this we recruited five families. In an attempt to recruit from children, we contacted different schools; this, however, did not prove successful. More successfully, we used local Facebook groups and the Faculty of Educational Sciences' Facebook page to inform of the project, asking people to contact us. In addition, we used our personal networks to help recruit participants.

In the first phase of the recruiting process, our only criteria was that the family included three generations and that at least one child of the family was between the ages 8-18. Halfway through the recruiting process, we adjusted the strategy to make sure we obtained a more diverse sample regarding particularly educational level and immigration background. In this phase, we would also ask first generation students and students with immigrant backgrounds from the Department of Education to recruit acquaintances and their families.

Recruitment sources:

- Seniornett – 5 families by first recruiting the grandparents
- Personal networks – 6 families by the parents
- Local Facebook group – 1 family by the mother
- Colleagues/UiO Facebook advertisement – 3 families by the parents
- Master students – 4 families by the grandparent or parents

For the T2 interviews, we aimed to recruit families from the PlatFAMs sample where all three generations lived in relatively close proximity to one another, and who had a certain level of reflexivity and use of digital platforms. We thus recruited two families with differing levels of education, and where one were all located in close proximity to one another, while the other had transnational family networks.

Country specific data management requirements and ethical considerations

Regarding data management requirements, the Norwegian team submitted a notification form for personal data to SIKT, Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research before the data collection was initiated. SIKT will assess the processing of personal data based on our description and give recommendations for the project to be able to meet requirements in data protection legislation.

Consent: The joint information sheet and consent form was translated to Norwegian and submitted to SIKT, who had some comments. We then included some recommended standard formulations for the Norwegian participants.

The Norwegian team had several ethical considerations related to data gathering. First, in some cases, the mother and/or father were present during the interviews with the youngest participants when they preferred. Second, in acknowledging that some of the youngest children might not have the patience to answer all questions, the interview guide was shortened considerably and most interviews with the youngest lasted only 30-40 minutes. Third, not all parents and grandparents were proficient in the Norwegian or English language. One grandparent needed their child (parent-generation) to help translate questions and answers, meaning that the parent heard all answers the grandparent provided. One parent participated and replied to all questions in Norwegian. However, due to her rather limited understanding of Norwegian language, the interviewer needed to be careful in asking the questions in a basic manner, explaining terms and adding follow up questions to ensure that her response was understood correctly.

Sample of informants

The sample includes 55 individuals. The first round of recruitment yielded a less diverse sample of families than desired, and special efforts were made to recruit parents with immigration backgrounds and parents/grandparents with lower SES/no higher education.

Summing up, the sample of parents reflect the general population of the Oslo area/east Norway regarding educational level and immigration background. Official statistics are not readily available, but it seems that blended/divorced/single parent households are slightly underrepresented. In the grandparent generation, people with higher education are highly overrepresented.

Generations

Among the 19 families, 17 were represented by all three generations. In one of the two families where the grandparent generation was not represented, the grandparents were living abroad in parts of the world where there were military unrest and poor internet connections. However, in both cases the parent generation were also grandparents and during the interview they also talked about keeping in contact with these grandchildren.

Age and gender

The age span of the sample is from 7 to 82 years. One 7-year-old child was included as their family helped diversify the sample. The youngest grandparent was 55, while the oldest parent was 58 years. However, the parent generation age span was from 33 to 58, with a mean of 45 years and a median of 51. The mean of the grandparent generation was 74 years (median 78).

Among the interviewees, there were 25 men/boys and 30 women/girls, and this balance roughly reflects the distribution of gender in all three generations.

Ethnic/minority background

Of the 19 represented families, seven (36%) included members either with immigration background or included a member of the parent generation with a mixed or minority ethnic background. Thus, the sample includes two grandparents, six parents of immigrant/mixed ethnic backgrounds, and six children defining themselves as either of mixed or of immigrant backgrounds (25.5% of the total sample). We were not able to recruit any grandparents living abroad. The sample reflects the ethnic composition of the population in Norway.

Area of residence

Only one of the grandparents was living with their children/grandchildren in the same household. Among the grandparents, two lived in a rural area, six lived in a small town, 2 lived in a - relative to Norwegian standards - large city (pop 50 000-200 000) and six (32%) lived in the capital city of Oslo. Among the parents and children, 10 families (50%) lived in Oslo, one family in another large city (pop 50 000-60 000), four lived in a small town and four in a rural area.

To be able to conduct the interviews mainly face to face, and thereby more easily allow interviewees to interact with the app logos, we chose to recruit most families from the eastern part of Norway/greater Oslo area. Thus, apart from two interviewees, all lived within a two and a half hour train ride from Oslo in all directions.

Educational level of parents and grandparents

The general level of education in Norway is high. Among the grandparents 11 of the 17 (65%) had completed upper secondary school as their highest level of education. In the parent generation 14 of the 19 had completed higher education (74%). Given that only 27% of the general Norwegian population in the age groups from 67 years and older has completed a university degree (SSB 2024), this group is highly overrepresented in the grandparent generation. The comparative share in the 30-50 age group is 50.2% (SSB 2024), which is slightly lower than the sample of the parent generation, in particular for the greater Oslo area.

Family structure

Among the parents' families (second generation) the majority were either divorced, one parent or 'blended' families, including stepchildren, foster children, and other children that were considered family. Three families included divorced parents only in the grandparent generation, which sometimes represented a challenge for family communication. Same-sex and one-parent households are underrepresented in the Norwegian sample.

Based on the second generation, seven of the families included three or more children. Most (53%) included two children while two families included one child. Some of the children reported more siblings than their parents included children, due to the inclusion of half siblings in another household, or other family members that were included as "siblings".

Based on the second generation, the sample consists of three father-son dyads, five father-daughter dyads, five mother-daughter dyads, and six mother-son dyads. Of these 19 families, eleven include three biologically related generations, and five of these were patri- or matrilinear generations.

Interviews

Time period

All interviews were conducted in the first half of 2024; starting from mid-March to the beginning of July. The pilot interviews were conducted mid December 2023.

The interviews were conducted by Kristinn Hegna (25), Maja Nordtug (23), and Ola Erstad (7).

Length of interviews

The length of the interviews varied from 30 minutes (due to other appointment) to up to 3 hours. The grandparent generation were interviewed for 1h 20 minutes up to 3 hours, while the children generation's interviews lasted from 35-45 minutes with the youngest children, up to 1 hour 50 minutes with the older children.

Location

Most interviews with the parents' generation were conducted in the interviewees' homes, and the grandparent was occasionally interviewed in the same home. Thus, among the grandparents 9 of the 17 were interviewed outside their own home. Two of these were online interviews, the others in their other family member's home, the library, in a local volunteering centre, in the church, or at the University of Oslo. Of the parent generation, 8 of the 19 were interviewed in their own home, the others mostly at the University of Oslo but also in the grandparent's home, at a public library, at a local volunteering centre, and at their place of work.

Transcription and de-individualisation

All interviews were transcribed by Autotekst within Educloud, using the NB Whisper solution to transcribe from audio to Norwegian language. The Autotekst AI transcription software is not connected to the internet. The transcripts were downloaded as plain text, using diarization to separate between speaker 1 (interviewer) and speaker 2 (interviewee). All transcripts were checked manually by a research assistant (in total, three research assistants were involved in this work).

De-individualisation/anonymisation

All transcripts were de-individualised by replacing all personal names, place names, and other personal information that could identify the individual. All families were given a specific family name pseudonym starting with letters from A to S (19 families). Within each family, the personal names that were occurring in more than one interview were given the same first name pseudonym, so that a grandfather's son's name was given the same pseudonym as the grandchild's corresponding uncle or father respectively.

All place names that were possible identifiers were replaced by descriptors, keeping vital information and generalising to a larger geographical area. Thus, the town Egersund would be replaced by [town on the south-west coast], or the rural area Rakkestad would be replaced with [rural area outside Oslo] etc. All alterations were listed in a family specific document which was stored in the family folder on a team specific secure server for Norway in Educloud, together with the audio files and the non-anonymised transcripts. Only the checked, anonymised transcripts were exported from Educloud.

Vocational or professional information that needed to be replaced for anonymity was replaced by a more general term for vocation/profession in which the level of education and socio-economic status was kept as similar as possible.

In some instances, personal information not relevant for the interview was omitted for privacy. Examples are diagnoses or information about members of the family that were figures in the Norwegian public sphere.